

DAMAGE MECHANICS OF CROSS-PLY LAMINATES RESULTING FROM TRANSVERSE CONCENTRATED LOADS

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ABSTRACT

A nonlinear three-dimensional finite element analysis was developed for investigating damage development inside Graphite/Epoxy cross-ply laminated composites resulting from quasi-static transverse loads. The major attention of the study was given to delamination evolution associated with two types of matrix cracks: a pair of internal cracks and a surface crack. An augmented Lagrangian method was utilized to model the delamination interface contact condition, coupled with a general contact node search algorithm which can handle complex contact conditions, such as arbitrary slippage and discontinuous curvature. No friction was considered in the analysis. Contact between the indenter and the laminate was also modeled. The strain energy release rates were calculated by a crack-closure technique and applied to determine the delamination propagation.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that fiber-reinforced composites are vulnerable to transverse concentrated loads such as low-velocity impact, which can result in extensive delaminations and multiple matrix cracking [1-7]. Numerous experimental and analytical investigations have been performed to study the damage resulting from transverse loads. More extensive literature is referred to [2,8]. The analytical work previously developed has emphasized estimating the overall delamination sizes [2,4,6,7,9]. None of these models considered the detailed fracturing process during the formation of the damage.

Several investigators have indicated based on their experiments that for some ply orientations, surface matrix cracking could be produced without generating delaminations by carefully adjusting the impact velocity or the amount of the applied load. However, whenever there was a delamination, there were matrix cracks accompanied with the delamination. An energy threshold also exists below which no damage could be generated. Experiments have demonstrated that similar results obtained from low-velocity impact tests could be produced by quasi-static transverse loads [1, 3, 5].

Joshi and Sun [5], among others, have suggested that matrix cracking is the initial impact damage mode. Basically, the initial matrix cracks have been classified by several investigators [5, 6] into two types: the internal shear crack and surface bending crack. However, work performed on studying the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination [10] has been limited to two-dimensional study. The fracture modes controlling delamination growth of laminated composites subjected to transverse concentrated loads have not yet been adequately identified. The author's 2-D study [8,11-13] showed that the initial matrix cracking affected significantly the growth of delamination. Delamination growth could be either stable or unstable depending upon the location of the initial matrix cracks. In a 3-D study, Lu and Liu [15] modeled an embedded circular delamination by a thin soft isotropic layer with a linear finite element method and showed that Mode II and Mode III fractures predominantly control the growth of the embedded delamination due to a point load. No matrix cracking was considered in their analysis. A recent study [14] by the author studied delamination growth induced by a surface crack of a T300/976 [0₆/90₂]_s laminate, and explained why the delamination grew into a peanut shape. However, the study on delamination growth induced by both internal cracks and surface cracks has not been reported.

Accordingly, the objective of the current investigation was to systematically study the damage mechanics of laminated composites subjected to transverse concentrated loading and to fundamentally understand the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination growth. To simplify the problem, only cross-ply laminated composite panels were studied, and the load was applied quasi-statically.

This paper will first present the analytical modeling. The comparison with the generated experimental data and numerical simulations will also be presented briefly. A detailed description of the analysis can be found in [8].

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II. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Consider a cross-ply laminated composite plate subjected to a quasi-static transverse concentrated loading as shown in Figure 1. The rectangular plates could be free or simply-supported or clamped on any one of the edges and subjected to a transverse quasi-static concentrated load by a spherical indenter. The plates were assumed to contain a pre-existing small delamination located at the central loading area on the second 90/0 interface directly beneath the indenter. Two types of matrix cracking in conjunction with the delamination were considered in the study: bending crack and a pair of shear cracks. Accordingly, for a given loading and boundary condition, four types of internal damage modes were studied: 1) delamination with no matrix cracks; 2) delamination induced by a bending crack; 3) delamination induced by shear cracks; and 4) delamination induced by both a bending crack and shear cracks, as shown in Figure 2. A typical damage pattern of the laminate from an X-radiograph is shown in Figure 3.

In this investigation, it was desired to determine

- 1). the effect of the initial matrix cracking on the propagation of the delamination in the plate,
- 2). the delamination growth in the laminate at a given load,
- 3). the fracture modes contributing to the delamination growth, and
- 4). the contact information associated with the delamination growth.

Accordingly, the laminate containing a delamination with a pair of pre-introduced internal cracks in the 90 degree ply group and with or without a surface crack in the 0 degree ply group was analyzed as shown in Figure 4. A three-dimensional finite element method was developed for analyzing the problem. A brief description of the analysis will be given in the next section, however, details of the analysis can be found in [8].

III. METHOD OF APPROACH

As the local deformations of the laminate could be substantial due to the concentrated load, finite deformation theory was adopted in the analysis. The total potential energy of a laminate without damage under the given load can be described as

$$\Pi = \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ply}} \int_{\Omega^m} W^m(E_{ij}^m) {}^o d\Omega - \int_{oS} {}^o \bar{T}_i \cdot u_i {}^o ds \quad (1)$$

where n_{ply} is the total number of layers, Ω^m is the cross-sectional area of the m th layer in the reference configuration, W is the strain energy function, u_i is the displacement vector, and oS is the boundary in the reference configuration where the tractions ${}^o \bar{T}_i$ are applied.

The components of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress in the m th layer can be expressed by the constitutive relation as

$$S_{ij}^m = C_{ijkl}^m E_{kl}^m \quad (2)$$

where E_{kl}^m are the components of Green's strain tensor. C_{ijkl}^m are the orthotropic material moduli for the m th layer.

Based on the virtual work principle, the following equation can be obtained from Eq. (1) for an uncracked laminate:

$$\delta \Pi = \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ply}} \int_{\Omega^m} S_{ij}^m \delta E_{ij}^m {}^o d\Omega - \int_{oS} {}^o \bar{T}_i \cdot \delta u_i {}^o ds = 0 \quad (3)$$

The above nonlinear equation is valid for any uncracked laminated composite undergoing finite deformations in three dimensions. However, for cracked laminates, Eq. (3) cannot be applied directly because of the presence of crack interfaces generated inside the materials. The contact condition of the interfacial contact during loading must be included in the analysis.

Two types of contact are involved: the rigid-elastic contact between the indenter and the plate, and the elastic-elastic contact between the cracked/delaminated interfaces, as shown in Figure 5. The local indentation resulting from a spherical indenter is very complicated and three-dimensional and could significantly affect the delamination growth and its interface deformation, especially when the delamination is small.

In order to prevent the contact surfaces from overlapping, an impenetrability condition must be specified and satisfied at all times along the contact interfaces. This condition requires that the shortest distance (defined as a gap g) between two contact surfaces must be greater than or equal to zero. Mathematically, the impenetrability constraint can be stated as $g \geq 0$. Upon contact, the contact force must also be less than or equal to zero ($\lambda_N \leq 0$). Accordingly, the contact constraints for normal contact can be specified as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \lambda_N &\leq 0 \\ g(u_i) &\geq 0 \\ \lambda_N g(u_i) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

This is the well-known Kuhn-Tucker conditions for normal contact. The three equations in Eq. (4) reflect,

that the pressure is nonzero only when $g = 0$. Accordingly, Eq. (4) must be considered together with Eq. (3) in order to analyze composites containing delaminations.

Several methods exist to implement the contact constraints. The most popular choices are the Lagrange multiplier method and the penalty method. Both methods have advantages and disadvantages (see discussions in [8]). The Lagrange multiplier method was adopted previously by the authors for the study of damage induced by a cylindrical indenter for analyzing the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination [13]. In this study, an augmented Lagrangian method was adopted. It has been shown to provide important advantages over the more traditional Lagrange multiplier and penalty methods. Detailed mathematical discussions can be found in [17]. The augmented Lagrangian techniques have been known to provide almost exact enforcement of constraints while using finite penalty parameters, avoiding the ill-conditioning.

In the method of augmented Lagrangians, the Lagrange multiplier λ_N is initially chosen to be an arbitrary constant. If this constant is not the correct Lagrange multiplier, the contact constraint is not satisfied and minimization of the total potential energy of Eq. (1) does not lead to the equation of equilibrium. Therefore, from a penalty function viewpoint, the total potential energy represented by Eq. (1) needs to be further penalized by the following modified functional:

$$\bar{\Pi} = \Pi + \int_{\Gamma} \lambda_N^{(k)} g \, d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_N g^2 \, d\Gamma \quad (5)$$

where $\lambda_N^{(k)} \leq 0$ denotes the fixed estimate of the correct λ_N . The superscript k indicates that the search for the correct λ_N is an iterative process. The updated formula is

$$\lambda_N^{(k+1)} = (\lambda_N^{(k)} + \epsilon_N g) \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the variational equation corresponding to Eq. (5) can be derived as

$$\delta\Pi + \int_{\Gamma} (\lambda_N^{(k)} + \epsilon_N g) \delta g \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad (7)$$

It is noted that the term $(\lambda_N^{(k)} + \epsilon_N g)$ plays the role of the Lagrange multiplier λ_N . If λ_N is the correct multiplier, then $g = 0$ on Γ . Thus, in the case where the multipliers are correct, Eq. (7) achieves exactly the same form as the standard Lagrange multiplier method, making it an exact penalization.

It is important to notice that Eq. (7) is a nonlinear equation due to the contact conditions and geometric nonlinearity. In general, then, it will be necessary to solve Eq. (7) in an iterative manner. In practice, ϵ_N is chosen to be as large as practically possible without inducing ill-conditioning. The advantage of the current treatment over the penalty method is that satisfaction of the constraints can be improved even if ϵ_N is of relatively modest value through repeated application of the augmentation procedure. Since these augmentations only change $\lambda_N^{(k)}$, which is fixed with regard to solution of Eq. (7), the ill-conditioning problem usually associated with the penalty method is mediated or eliminated.

A three-dimensional finite element method was developed based on Eq. (7), and an eight-node brick element was used. Due to symmetry, only a quarter of the laminate was analyzed. A typical finite element mesh is shown in Figure 6.

The initiation of delamination growth (onset of delamination growth) was predicted based on linear elastic fracture mechanics. The well-known virtual crack closure technique [16] served as the basis for the strain-energy release rate calculation. This procedure determines Mode I, Mode II, and Mode III strain energy release rates (G_I , G_{II} , and G_{III}) from the energy required to close the delamination over a small area.

Therefore, at any point on the delamination front, strain energy release rates can be calculated. Since the delamination growth can be attributed to a mixed mode fracture, the criterion for determining the initiation of the delamination growth was selected as [8]

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^{\alpha} + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^{\beta} + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}}\right)^{\gamma} = E_d \quad (8)$$

for any point on the delamination front. Here, G_{IC} , G_{IIC} , and G_{IIIC} are the critical strain energy release rates corresponding to Mode I, Mode II, and Mode III fracture, respectively. It was assumed that G_{IC} , G_{IIC} , and G_{IIIC} did not change with delamination size. Based on the previous two-dimensional study by the authors, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 1$, and $\gamma = 1$ were selected for this study, because they were found to provide the best fit to the experiments in two dimensions. It was assumed that $G_{IIIC} = G_{IIC}$ [18], because the value of G_{IIIC} has not been reported in the literature. Accordingly, delamination would start to propagate when $E_d \geq 1$ at any point on the delamination front.

IV. RESULTS AND COMPARISON

In order to verify the model, numerical solutions were generated and compared with existing analytical

be found in [8]. In the following, numerical simulations and experimental verification are presented and discussed.

It is observed that for $[0_2/90_6]_s$ layup, distinct matrix cracks (shear cracks) in the central 90 degree ply group near the loading area could be seen clearly in addition to the surface bending crack, and the delamination shape was fairly close to a semi-circular shape on each side which was quite unevenly distributed.

Type 3 and 4 models were used to study the delamination growth behavior in $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composites. The type 3 model simulates a delamination induced by a pair of shear cracks, while the type 4 model considers both a bending crack and shear cracks in conjunction with a delamination. Therefore, numerical calculations were generated for the laminate containing a delamination with various sizes and a shear crack in the middle 90° ply group with and without a surface bending crack in the bottom 0° ply group. As suggested by the experimental observation, the lengths of the matrix cracks were assumed to be slightly larger than the delamination length and width in the x and y directions throughout the calculations. In the following figures, similar to the $[0_6/90_2]_s$ case, numerical results will be presented for delaminations from small to large sizes.

A close-up view of a deformed cross-section ($X - Z, Y = 0$) of a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ panel at a load of 327 lbf is shown in Figure 7. The local indentation due to the rigid indenter and relatively large sliding between the two surfaces of the delamination and internal crack are clearly shown in Figure 7.

Figure 8 shows the sequence of the delamination growth in the laminate containing a pair of shear cracks predicted by the type 3 model. At the fixed indenter displacement, Figure 8-1 and Figure 8-2 show that the initial delamination grew from a small elliptical shape into a wider elliptical shape along the direction at $\phi = 90^\circ$ with its minor axis perpendicular to the fiber direction of the bottom ply group. The delamination growth was unstable because the strain energy release rates increased as the delamination expanded. Figure 8-3 indicates that the delamination began to expand along its major axis, as the strain energy release rate ratio started to decrease along the delamination front near $\phi = 90^\circ$ and had the highest value at the delamination front near $\phi = 0^\circ$.

The expansion of the delamination along its major or minor axis ceased to increase when the growth index E_d along the delamination front was below unity, as in the case shown in Figure 8-6. The delamination shape shown in Figure 8-6 is approximately a circular one, which agreed with the delamination shape of $[0_2/90_6]_s$ panels observed from the experiments (see Figure 3-b). Figure 9 shows the comparisons between the estimated delamination sizes in the x and y directions and the sizes measured from the experiments. The correlation between the experiments and the predictions was good.

It was interesting to evaluate the contributing fracture modes for the delamination growth in $[0_2/90_6]_s$ panels. Figure 10 shows the calculated strain energy release rates of Modes I, II, and III for the laminate containing a small delamination with an internal shear crack and a surface bending crack. For the laminate with the initial bending crack, G_I (Mode I fracture) contributed significantly to the total strain energy release rate along the delamination front near the neighborhood where the matrix cracks intersected with the delamination ($\phi = 0^\circ$ and 90°), indicating that delamination initiation was in mixed modes.

Figure 11 shows the calculated strain energy release rates of Modes I, II, and III for the laminate containing a larger delamination with an internal crack and with or without a surface matrix crack. Clearly, Modes II and III fractures dominated the total strain energy release rate for the laminate with and without the surface matrix crack. And it is noted that the total strain energy release rate was only slightly affected by the introduction of the surface crack, indicating that delamination growth was dominated by the internal shear crack.

Figure 12 shows a peculiar contact zone distribution for a typical delamination with both shear and bending cracks, indicating that a narrow portion near delamination front is closed or in sliding. It has been shown numerically that calculated energy release rates would be wrong if the contact model is not implemented, as overlapping naturally occurs at bi-material interface.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A finite element analysis was developed for analyzing cross-ply laminated composite plates subjected to transverse concentrated loading resulting from a spherical indenter. Based on the analysis, the following remarks can be made for the laminates studied:

- 1). The initial matrix cracking significantly affects the growth of delamination resulting from transverse loading.
- 2). Matrix cracks enhance delamination growth.
- 4). Mixed mode fracture dominates the internal crack induced small delamination growth. Mode II and III governs the internal crack induced large delamination growth.

Additionally, it is noted that the proposed finite element analysis can also be extended to study other ply orientations and other loading conditions, such as delamination buckling, which are going to be reported in future publications.

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Figure 1 Description of the problem. A laminated composite panel subjected to a transverse load applied by a spherically-nosed indenter.

Figure 3 An X-Radiograph of a graphite/epoxy $[0_2/90_6]_s$ resulting from a quasi-static transverse loading.

Figure 2 Four types of damage modes considered in this analysis: 1) delamination with no matrix cracks; 2) delamination induced by a bending crack; 3) delamination induced by shear cracks; and 4) delamination induced by both a bending crack and shear cracks.

Figure 4 The coordinate system used in the finite element analysis for a laminate containing a pair of shear cracks and one delamination having two semi-circular or semi-elliptical shapes offset by the internal cracks.

Figure 5 Contact problem associated with a delaminated laminate subjected to an indenter.

Figure 6 Description of a typical finite element mesh used in the analysis.

Figure 7 Deformation of a cross-section ($X-Z, Y = 0$) of a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite with a surface matrix crack.

Figure 8 The predicted delamination growth sequence in a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite containing a surface matrix crack and an internal matrix crack.

Figure 9 The comparison of delamination sizes predicted and measured in a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite with respect to quasi-impact energy.

Figure 10 Comparison of the calculated strain energy release rates of Modes I, II, and III along a small delamination front in a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite containing an internal crack and a surface matrix crack.

Figure 11 Comparison of the calculated strain energy release rates of Modes I, II, and III along a large delamination front in a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite containing an internal crack and with or without a surface matrix crack.

With Shear and Bending Cracks

Figure 12 Typical contact zone of a delamination in a $[0_2/90_6]_s$ composite containing an internal crack and with a surface matrix crack.